

THE PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE METHOD OF DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article explains the ideas that exist before children in mathematical concepts, organizes games outside of class time, and strengthens, deepens, and expands children's mathematical concepts. Questionnaire, question-answer, interview, generalization, observation methods are listed in the development of mathematical concepts.

Mathematics is both an interesting and a “harder to digest” science. In mastering it, of course, the skills of the educator in school and the educator in preschool education are tested. Of course, the first knowledge of mathematics is acquired in kindergarten. If mathematics is taught in school on the basis of lessons, mathematical concepts are developed through lessons in preschool education. While emphasizing skill, both the educator and the teacher need to master other subjects as well. In addition, children's mathematical knowledge helps them to explore the world more deeply, more fully, without being separated from life. This is why children are introduced to ideas that exist before mathematical concepts.

In extracurricular activities, children's mathematical imaginations are strengthened, deepened, and expanded by organizing games. By the way, issues also have a place in mathematics. In particular, the child or student should acquire geographical, economic, cultural and national knowledge through issues. For example: My brother had

two apples. I gave him ten more apples to fill his basket. How many apples did he have? Two rounds of conclusions can be drawn from the solution. Firstly, the increase in the number of apples, and secondly, the fact that the number of apples benefited my brother, the brother's generosity to his brother makes one happy. In other words, if the educator discovers a new problem-solving method in the child, an interesting problem-solving method, abandoning the standard methods he has always used, new solutions to the problem, understanding the essence of the problem and finding different ways to solve it, helps in the development of mathematical concepts if you have the ability to give.

Children's mathematical imaginations are strengthened, deepened, and expanded even when organized through extracurricular games. It is very important that the knowledge that children acquire is constantly reinforced in daily life, play, work, marriage, as well as other activities. Didactic games: folk didactic games, games in which pyramids are played with other toys play an important

role in strengthening knowledge. The child should have a relatively good knowledge of numbers, shapes and sizes of objects, be able to target in space (2 and 3 dimensions) and time. The educator should try to cultivate in children a priority (constant) interest in mathematical knowledge, the ability to use them and the desire to acquire them independently.

It is especially important to develop independent thinking, spatial imagination in children at this age. The child should be able to draw conclusions in solving problems, to find ways to solve problems. When solving problems, it is important that the educator teaches to solve the most convenient and simple problems. In preschool education, each lesson should have a goal in mind. In order for the training to be sufficiently satisfactory and successful, the educator must have a clear understanding and mastery of the general educational, pedagogical and developmental goals and objectives of the training, as well as the methods of its implementation.

In the process of solving problems in the classroom, each child should have a system of mathematical knowledge, special and general learning skills and abilities, a level of development and upbringing, which will allow him to develop independent thinking. Teaching math helps children to speak their mother tongue fluently, to express their thoughts clearly and fluently. It is impossible to be careless in describing mathematics, and it is especially important to be able to use each word in its proper place. That is why mathematics is based on concrete knowledge, not 'extortion'. It also works when the approximate method is used to solve mathematical problems. This allows the child to predict the accuracy of the solution with some degree of accuracy.

In short, in addition to the methods listed above, the use of questionnaires, question-answer, conversation, generalization, observation, pedagogical experiment methods is also effective in the development of problems, mathematical concepts at school age. In addition, before the child goes to school, it is necessary to carry out special work, independently linking it with all the educational work in the MTM, in order to form mathematical concepts in him. Mathematical knowledge should be imparted to children in a certain system and sequence, with new knowledge to a lesser extent, that is, to the extent that children can assimilate it. The educator must know how the program is structured for each age group, all the work that is done to develop basic mathematical skills in preschool children, and the importance of each lesson.

Most of the program tasks are solved in the lessons. In children, in a certain sequence, perceptions are formed, the necessary skills and abilities are formed. It is necessary to pay attention to the organization of quantitative observations of everything around, how children use their knowledge and skills in the mathematical context in different types of activities. It is necessary to make extensive use of didactic games and exercises in the lessons, to organize games outside the lessons, to strengthen, deepen and expand children's mathematical imagination. The provision of MTCs with highly educated specialists and the organization of classes using innovative pedagogical technologies will give effective results. Development of textbooks, didactic materials, manuals and technical aids for mathematical teaching aids (what to teach).

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